

HYGIENE AND ACTIVITY OF GAMES ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN HEALTH

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Annotation: This article provides full information about movement games, importance of movement games in human health, hygiene and wellness.

Keywords: action, game, child, exercise, rule, exercise, fitness, condition, physical exercise, action games

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada harakatli o'yinlar, harakatli o'yinlarning inson salomatligi, gigevenik va sog'lomlashtirishdagi ahamiyati haqida to'liq ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: harakat, o'yin, bola, mashq, qoida, mashg'ulot, sog'lomlashtirish, holat, jismoniy mashqlar, harakatli o'yinlar

Аннотация: в данной статье представлена полная информация о подвижных играх, значении подвижных игр для здоровья человека, гигиены и хорошего самочувствия.

Ключевые слова: действие, игра, ребенок, упражнение, правило, упражнение, приспособленность, состояние, физическое упражнение, подвижные игры.

The main content of action games is the movement of players and various movements. When it is properly managed, they have an effective effect on other systems of the body and respiratory, muscular, cardiovascular systems. It increases the functional activity of active games, engages various dynamic activities in various large and small muscles of the body, and increases the mobility of the joints. Especially from the point of view of health of the players, it is important that active games should be held in the open air in all seasons.[1]

Under the influence of physical exercises used in the game, metabolism is activated in every way (carbohydrate, protein, fat and minerals). Muscle work enhances the functions of endocrine glands. Taking into account the physical fitness and age characteristics of the participants, it is possible to have the hygienic and health-improving value that such active games help only when the training is set correctly. It should be taken into account that the possibility of accurate distribution of the load in action games is limited, because there is no possibility to know in advance the readiness of each participant of the game. The constantly changing situation in the game, high-intensity interaction, does not allow to precisely regulate the size and direction of the load if the content of the exercise is not included in the program from some of the game participants.

Therefore, it is necessary to monitor the physical load to be optimal. When playing regularly, he can apply intense load, because the children's body must gradually adapt to it. [2]

The game should have an effective effect on the nervous system of the participants. This is achieved by providing an optimal load, as well as the organization of the game in such a way that it causes positive mental experiences in the players, the poor organization of the game leads to negative mental experiences, the normal functioning of nervous processes is disturbed stress (strong excitement) appears, which harms health.

The rules of action games regulate the interaction of the participants of the game and eliminate their excessive excitement. Clear and impartial refereeing according to the rules of the game creates positive mental experiences in the players. The regular use of action games helps to develop a dynamic stereotype in the nervous system, which makes it easier to perform the action. [3]

The fact that the game is held in the open air (weather permitting), especially in the summer and winter seasons, helps children to exercise. Currently, hypodynamia is increasing in the young generation due to the increasing flow of information, the increase in the time of training sessions, demonstration of movement, the need to exert muscle, and the decrease in the activity of movement.[4] The extensive use of active play helps to reduce hypodynamia, as it compensates for³ the lack of movement activity. In an action game, players can actively relax after a long period of mental activity. It is used for this purpose during the break at school, during a walk on the playground after the end of the lesson (in a group with an extended day), at home after returning from school, and after preparing the lesson.

Active games should be held at school in small classes as much as possible in the form of timed physical education (physical education) during the lesson, because 7-8-year-old children are stressed for 45 minutes, especially in the last lessons of the school day, which is very difficult.[5] A short movement game played with children at the desk changes the work of the nerve centers, allows relaxation (inhibits the excitation of the nerve centers) and activates muscle activity.

When children's physical development lags behind, it is necessary to use active games, because it helps to make the body healthy, increases the general level of physical development. Action games are used in sanatoriums and inpatients for the purpose of special treatment to restore the health of sick children. It helps to

increase the functionality and enthusiasm that occurs in children during the game.

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